

Quantum Bound Information $\ln(W)$, $\ln(a(p)a(x))$ as Statistical Constant Vectors over Variables x, p ?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 5. 2022

For a classical ideal gas or single particle quantum system with energy levels $\{e_i\}$, both average energy $E = \sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ and Shannon's entropy $S = - \sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(P(e_i/T))$ change (for mechanical parameters kept fixed) in terms of $d(P(e_i/T))$. In fact, in this case $\ln(P(e_i/T))$ appears as a "constant vector" in dS i.e. $dS = - \sum_i \ln(P(e_i/T)) dP(e_i/T)$. Both dE (mechanical parameter fixed) and dS change as $dP(e_i/T)$, thus there are two vectors $\{e_i/T\}$ and $\{\ln(P(e_i/T))\}$ which represent constants over e_i 's for a small range of dT where T is temperature. In this case, however, the two vectors are strongly linked as $P(e_i/T) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)$ so $\ln(P) = -e_i/T - \ln(C)$. This is why the relationship $E - TS = -T \ln(C(T))$ exists.

For a quantum bound state one may write: $e = \int dp a(p)a(x) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \int dx V(x) W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction. Instead of having vectors of e_i 's, one has two vectors, one over x and the other p (momenta) where $a(p)a(p) = P(p)$ and $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ (bound states). Thus $de_{\text{thermal}} = \int dp \frac{p^2}{2m} dP(p) + \int dx V(x) dP(x)$ ((1)). In other words de_{thermal} changes linearly in terms of $dP(p)$ and $dP(x)$ whereas for a classical ideal gas or many e_i system it changes linearly in terms of $dP(e_i/T)$. e_i is the variable instead of x and p in that case. In other words $\{p^2/2m\}$ is a constant vector in p space and $\{V(x)\}$ in x space.

Mathematically Shannon's entropy $S_p = - \sum_p P(p) \ln(P(p))$ and $S_x = - \sum_x P(x) \ln(P(x))$ also yield constant vectors in their respective spaces namely $\ln(P(p))$ and $\ln(P(x))$ which are called information. In particular $dS_p = - \sum_p \ln(P(p)) dP(p)$ then $\ln(P(p))$ behaves like a constant vector within a region of small $dP(p)$ changes. Note: $\sum_p dP(p) = 0$. One may consider a set of single valued energy levels e_i which are very close (imagine a particle in a box with infinite walls) as a region in which $dP(p)$ changes (or $dP(x)$ ones) are very small. In this region, $\ln(P(p))$ and $\ln(P(x))$, information, represents a constant vector statistically defining the small region of e_i states. This we argue is the statistical significance of information $\ln(P)$. One may note that both de_{thermal} and dS_p and dS_x change linearly with $dP(p)$ and $dP(x)$, but the vectors $\{p^2/2m\}$ and $\{V(x)\}$ over p and x space and $\ln(P(p))$ and $\ln(P(x))$ over the same space are constant vectors, but not equivalent except for the ground state of the quantum oscillator for which they become very similar because $P(p) = \exp(-ap)$ and $P(x) = \exp(-xx/a)$ with a being proportional to $1/e$ which plays the same role as temperature in the classical ideal gas case. For other quantum bound systems, the two sets of vectors are different, but the information vectors seem to give a kind of statistical identity to small regions containing very close e_i levels for which $dP(p)$ and $dP(x)$ are small. Thus, though one may argue for the presence of $\ln(P)$ in Shannon's entropy $S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ in many ways, it seems that $\ln(P(i))$ is a constant vector in a certain space i for small $dP(i)$ and gives a statistical identity to that small region.

Various Arguments for the Presence of ln in Shannon's Entropy

The function ln has an interesting additive property $\ln(AB) = \ln(A) + \ln(B)$ as well as a derivative property $d/dx \ln(P(x)) = 1/P dP/x$. The additive property is useful in that one may define Shannon's entropy for product probabilities $P_1(i)P_2(j)$ as $-\sum_{i,j} P_1(i)P_2(j) \ln(P_1(i)P_2(j)) = -\sum_i P_1(i) \ln(P_1(i)) - \sum_j P_2(j) \ln(P_2(j))$ i.e. obtain additive entropies. This may be given as a reason to use ln in Shannon's entropy. Alternatively for a bound quantum state depending on a parameter such as L for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls or k a spring constant, $P_e(x)$ goes as $1/L$ and $P_e(p)$ as L so using Shannon's entropy ensures that the mechanical parameter disappears from $S_p + S_x = S$ allowing for a quantum adiabatic transformation to also be isentropic. The derivative property is useful if one considers $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)$ where $C(T)$ is the normalization constant. Then $dE = T dT d/dT \ln(C)$. If one wishes to have dE depend on a linear differential of a new function S i.e. $dE = \text{constant } dS$, then $\ln(P(e_i/T))$ appears.

In this note we use the derivative property to argue that $\ln(P(i))$ called information defines a constant vector in i space within a region of small $dP(i)$. In other words it defines the statistical nature of this small region with changes being given by

$$dS = - \sum_i \ln(P(i)) dP(i) \quad ((3))$$

$\ln(P(i))$ i.e. Information in Entropy as Statistically Defining Small $dP(i)$ Regions

Consider $E = E_{\text{average}} = \sum_i e_i P(e_i)$. Then a thermal change in E (holding mechanical parameters constant) is:

$$dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, dE changes linearly with $dP(e_i)$ and the vector $\{e_i\}$ in e_i space is constant within a region of small $dP(e_i)$. $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / C(T)$ so $dE = dE/dT dT$. In other words e_i is a constant vector in a region of dT helping to define energy. The vector $dP(e_i)$ defines the change in energy.

Due to the derivative property $d/dx \ln(P(x)) = 1/P dP/dx$ one has:

$$D \sum_x P(x) \ln(P(x)) = \sum_x \ln(P(x)) dP(x) \quad ((5))$$

because $\sum_x dP(x) = 0$ and $\sum_x P(x) = 1$. In other words $\ln(P(x))$ behaves as a constant vector within a region of small $dP(x)$. $\{\ln(P(x))\}$ is a vector over x and so as a constant it gives a kind of statistical identity to this region. Thus $\{\ln(P(e_i/T))\}$ should be the information vector giving statistical identity in the region dT linked to ((4)). One may note that:

$$dS = - \sum_i \ln(P(e_i/T)) dP(e_i/T) \quad ((6)) \text{ like } ((4)) \text{ is linear in } dP(e_i).$$

In fact, one may try to make $\ln(P(e_i/T))$ almost equal to e_i i.e. $\ln(\exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)) = -e_i/T - \ln(C(T))$. Multiplying by T i.e. $dE = T dS$ (thermal changes) allows for this as does:

$$E-TS = -\ln(C(T)) \quad ((7))$$

Quantum Bound State Information

How do the above ideas pertain to a quantum bound state which contains a single e and not a set of e_i ? In such a case, one does not deal with e_i space, but rather with two spaces, x and p . In particular:

$$e = \sum \over p \ a(p)a(p) \ p^2/2m + \sum \over x \ W(x)W(x) \ V(x) \quad ((8))$$

Here $W(x) = \sum \over p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction and $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$. One may note that $W(x) = We(x)$ because one has a wavefunction corresponding to an energy level e . Then:

$$de = \sum \over p \ \ p^2/2m \ dPe(p) + \sum \over x \ V(x) \ dPe(x) \quad ((9))$$

This is similar to ((4)), but one has two vectors in two different spaces: $\{p^2/2m\}$ in p space and $\{V(x)\}$ in x space.

Given the nature of $d/dx \ln(Pe(x))$ and $d/dp \ln(Pp(p))$, Shannon's entropies also change linearly with $dPe(x)$ and $dPe(p)$ i.e.

$$S = - \sum \over x \ Pe(x)\ln(Pe(x)) - \sum \over p \ Pe(p)\ln(Pe(p)) \quad ((10)) \text{ and}$$

$$dS = - \sum \over x \ \ln(Pe(x)) \ dPe(x) - \sum \over p \ \ln(Pe(p)) \ dPe(p) \quad ((11))$$

For quantum bound states, unlike for the case of ((4)) one cannot usually closely link $\ln(Pe(x))$ with $V(x)$ and $\ln(Pe(p))$ with $p^2/2m$. There is one case, however, where one can, namely the ground state of the harmonic oscillator for which:

$$Pe(x) \text{ is proportional to } \exp(-axx) \text{ and } Pe(p) \text{ is proportional to } \exp(-pp/a) \quad ((12))$$

where a is proportional to e_0 (ground state energy) which behaves like the classical T (temperature).

In general, however, the two information vectors $\{\ln(Pe(x))\}$ and $\{\ln(Pe(p))\}$ in x and p space are not easily linked to de , but are nevertheless statistical constant vectors within small $dPe(x)$ and $dPe(p)$ regions. To consider such regions, imagine e_i levels which are very close to each other (e.g. consider a particle in a box with infinite potential walls for which $e = bnn/LL$ where b is a constant, L the box size is kept constant and n is an integer. For high n regions, e_n levels are very close and $\{\ln(Pe_n(x))\}$ and $\{\ln(Pe_n(p))\}$ represent constant vectors within these small regions. In other words they give a statistical identity to such regions. Thus we argue that $\ln(P(i))$ where i

represents a space (e.g. e_i space, x space, p space) has statistical meaning as it behaves as a constant vector in this region much like an e average for a set of closely spaced e_i represents a de region.

Alternative Equations

((8)) mixes $dPe(x)$ and $dPe(p)$ in the same equation. If one wishes to have equations with only $Pe(x)$ or $Pe(p)$ one may consider their counterparts $a_e(p)$ and $We(x)$.

If one writes $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ in the time-independent Schrodinger and collects coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ then:

$$a(p)a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum_k a(p) a(p-k) V_k = e a(p)a(p) \quad ((13))$$

One may sum over p and using $Pe(p) = a(p)a(p)$ write $\frac{p^2}{2m} dPe(p)$ for the first term and $e dPe(p)$ for the RHS, but the second term on the LHS remains complicated.

Alternatively, one may consider only x coordinates with $W(x) = W_0(x) + dW(x)$ for a change in W linked to $dPe(x)$ where $Pe(x) = WW$. From the time-independent Schrodinger equation one has:

$$de = -\frac{1}{2m} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW_0/dx}{W_0} - \frac{dW}{W_0} \right) - \frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dW}{dx} \frac{1}{W_0} \right) \quad ((14))$$

Here de is the difference in energy between e_0 and e_1 with the two being very close. In other words e_0 is really e_n and e_1 , e_{n+1} . This equation involves d/dx d/dx of (dW) and hence of $Pe(x)$ and so also is not convenient.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although there are various ways to argue for a $\ln(P(i))$ factor in Shannon's entropy (some of the based on $\ln(AB) = \ln(A) + \ln(B)$) we argue that the derivative property $d/dx \ln(P(x)) = 1/P dP/dx$ leads to information $\ln(P(i))$ behaving as a constant vector in Shannon's entropy $S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ i.e. $dS = - \sum_i \ln(P(i)) dP(i)$. Thus $\ln(P(i))$ information is a vector in i space which is constant in a region of small $dP(i)$. We argue that it statistically defines this region.

dE (thermal) = $\sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$ is also linear in $dP(e_i)$ and so for the case of $S = - \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$, one may set $\ln(P(e_i))$ to being very close to e_i which is what happens with $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)$. This is why $E - TS = -\ln(C(T))$ i.e. one does not simply have $dE_{thermal} = TdS$, but an equation with E and S on the same footing.

For quantum bound states, we argue that there are two information vectors $\{\ln(Pe(x))\}$ in x space and $\{\ln(Pe(p))\}$ in p space. For a single bound state $e = \sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} Pe(p) + \sum_x V(x) Pe(x)$. Thus $de_{thermal}$ is linear in $dPe(p)$ and $dPe(x)$. One may also create Shannon's entropy $S_p + S_x = - \sum_p Pe(p) \ln(Pe(p)) - \sum_x Pe(x) \ln(Pe(x))$ and $dS = - \sum_p \ln(Pe(p)) dPe(p) - \sum_x \ln(Pe(x)) dPe(x)$. This is also linear in $dPe(x)$ and $dPe(p)$, but in only one case may one link the two as in classical physics and that is the ground state oscillator for which $Pe(x) = \exp(-axx)$ and $Pe(p) = \exp(-pp/a)$ where a is proportional

to e. Nevertheless the information vectors $\{ \ln(Pe(x)) \}$ and $\{ \ln(Pe(p)) \}$ in x and p space are constant in regions of small $dPe(x)$ and $dPe(p)$ and statistically define these regions we argue. For example one may have a set of e_i levels which are very close together as in the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. Thus $\ln(P_i)$ has statistical significance on its own.